

Statistical DownScaling Model

Downscaling of precipitation data with SDSM

quick start guide

April 2022.

Project:

EXTremeClimTwin

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952384

“Twinning for the advancement of data-driven multidisciplinary research into hydro-climatic extremes to support risk assessment and decision making”

Acknowledgements

The [ExtremeClimTwin Project](#) is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952384.

[SDSM](#) was created by **Robert L. Wilby** (Department of Geography and Environment, Loughborough University, UK) and **Christian W. Dawson** (Department of Computer Science, Loughborough University, UK)

This document was compiled by Minučer Mesaroš ([Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad](#))

SDSM Version 4.2 was supported by the Environment Agency of England and Wales as part of the Thames Estuary 2100 project.

SDSM Version 3.1 was supported by the Environment Agency of England and Wales as part of the Climate Impacts and Adaptation Research Programme. The UKSDSM data archive was updated by Ian Harris (Climate Research Unit) and now includes data kindly supplied by the UK Hadley Centre, CSIRO Atmospheric Research, and the Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis.

SDSM Version 2.2 was sponsored by the Environment Agency through the National Centre for Risk Analysis and Options Appraisal.

SDSM Version 2.1 was supported by the Canadian Climate Impacts Scenarios (CCIS) Group through the Climate Change Action Fund. Assistance in kind was provided by A Consortium for the Application of Climate Impact Assessments (ACACIA) at the National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). NCAR is sponsored by the U.S. National Science Foundation.

NCEP Re-analysis data were provided by the NOAA-CIRES Climate Diagnostics Center, Boulder, Colorado, USA, from their Web site at <http://www.cdc.noaa.gov/>

The Climate Impacts LINK Project is funded by the UK Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions (Contract Reference EPG 1/1/124).

CONTENTS

1. PREFACE.....	3
2. SDSM WORKFLOW OVERVIEW	4
3. DATA SOURCES AND STRUCTURE	5
4. RUNNING THE PROGRAM, SETUP AND QUALITY CONTROL.....	7
4.1 QUALITY CONTROL.....	8
5. SCREENING OF PREDICTOR VARIABLES	9
5.1 NCEP daily predictor variable codes and definitions.....	10
6. MODEL CALIBRATION.....	12
7. WEATHER GENERATION (USING OBSERVED PREDICTORS).....	14
8. STATISTICAL ANALYSES	15
9. GRAPHING MODEL OUTPUT.....	19
10. SCENARIO GENERATION (without CLIMATE MODEL input).....	24
11. APPENDIX 1 – RESOLVING ISSUES WITH RUNNING THE SOFTWARE.....	25

1. PREFACE

This guide was created based on lectures given by Prof. Robert Wilby (Department of Geography, Loughborough University, UK) during Workshops of the [EXTremeClimTwin Project](#) (European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Grant agreement No 952384) and the original [SDSM software manual \(V. 4.2\)](#) (Wilby and Dawson, 2007.).

The recording of the lectures can be found on the [EXTremeClimTwin Project YouTube channel](#)

For full reference on theoretical background and more detailed technical guides please check the available instruction materials on the SDSM website:

<https://sdsml.org.uk/software.html>

The Statistical DownScaling Model (SDSM) facilitates the rapid development of multiple, low-cost, single-site scenarios of daily and sub-daily surface weather variables under present and future climate forcing. Additionally, the software performs ancillary tasks of data quality control and transformation, predictor variable pre-screening, automatic model calibration, basic diagnostic testing, statistical analyses, extreme value estimation and graphing of climate data.

2. SDSM WORKFLOW OVERVIEW

1. Quality control and data transformation
2. Screening of predictor variables
3. Model calibration
4. Weather generation (using observed predictors)
5. Statistical analyses
6. Graphing model output
7. Scenario generation (using climate model predictors)

**SDSM-DC
architecture
(version 5)**

Figure 1. The SDSM data processing and analysis algorithm (Wilby, 2021.)

3. DATA SOURCES AND STRUCTURE

All files used in this exercise can be downloaded from Zenodo via the following

DOI:

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591935>

SDSM works with ASCII files.

For the purposes of this guide, we will use **daily precipitation data recorded at the Belgrade meteorological station between 01.01.1961. and 31.12.2017** (BelgradePrecOBS.txt).

The working folder will be C:/sds/

Predictor variables from the NCEP Re-analysis are available from 01.01.1948. For Belgrade, missing value data identifiers (-999) must be added manually for the period between 1948 and 1961. This can be done in a spreadsheet by creating a list of days and filling in the missing values.

	A	B	C			
1	01/01/1948	-999		25559	22/12/2017	0
2	02/01/1948	-999		25560	23/12/2017	0.2
3	03/01/1948	-999		25561	24/12/2017	0.1
4	04/01/1948	-999		25562	25/12/2017	0
5	05/01/1948	-999		25563	26/12/2017	0
6	06/01/1948	-999		25564	27/12/2017	0
7	07/01/1948	-999		25565	28/12/2017	0
8	08/01/1948	-999		25566	29/12/2017	0
9	09/01/1948	-999		25567	30/12/2017	0
				25568	31/12/2017	0

Figure 2. Padding the missing data values with -999 in Excel

The SDSM input format requires a text file with data values given in a **single column**:


```

BelgradePrecOBS.txt - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
-999
-999
-999
-999
-999
-999
-999
0
0
0
0
0.2
0
0.1
0
0
Ln 4749, Col 5    100%    Windows (CRLF)    UTF-8
  
```

Figure 3. The required structure of the observed data file for use in SDSM

Check the text file for unnecessary empty lines, special characters or spaces and remove them. The total number of lines should be 25568, with 4749 missing value code (-999) and 20819 valid data points for the Belgrade station (1.1.1948 – 31.12.2017).

Predictor variables can be downloaded from the SDSM site by entering the Longitude and Latitude coordinates for the analyzed meteorological station (Belgrade Lon:20.46666, Lat:44.8).

<https://sdsml.org.uk/data.html>

Figure 4. Downloading the NCEP predictor variables using the latitude, longitude coordinates in decimal degrees format

Copy and unzip the downloaded **BOX_45N_20E.zip** file in the working folder (C:\sdsml\BOX_45N_20E)

Figure 5. The folder with the downloaded predictor files

4. RUNNING THE PROGRAM, SETUP AND QUALITY CONTROL

After running SDSM open **Settings** (if you experience problems with running the program, please see [APPENDIX 1. for possible solutions](#))

Figure 6. Main menu of SDSM 6.1

Figure 7. The *Settings* screen

Make sure the **Start date** is set to **01/01/1948**, **End date** to **31/12/2017**, the **Missing Data Identifier** to **-999**, the **Event Threshold** to **0**, and **Allow Negative Values** is turned off (when downscaling variables such as precipitation which has only positive values). Set the **Default File Directory** to **C:/sdsm**.

After setting all options, select **Save**.

4.1 QUALITY CONTROL

Quality Control

File Edit Help

Home → Quality Control → Transform Data → Screen Variables → Calibrate Model
 Scenario Generator → Summary Statistics → Compare Results → Frequency Analysis → Time Series Analysis

Reset Check File Daily Stats Outliers Settings

Select File

Select File

File: BelgradePrecOBS.txt

Pettitt Test

Minimum annual data threshold (%)

Threshold

Apply Threshold

Outliers

Standard Deviations:

Select File

File: Not selected

Results

Minimum:	0
Maximum:	107.9
Mean:	1.89743
Number of values in file:	25568
Missing values:	4749
Number of values ok:	20819
Maximum difference:	93.6
Maximum difference value 1:	0.4
Maximum difference value 2:	94
Values over threshold:	7904
Pettitt test (significance):	1.14840
Pettitt maximum position:	N/A
Missing value code:	-999
Event threshold:	0

Figure 8. The Quality control screen

5. SCREENING OF PREDICTOR VARIABLES

Open the **Screen Variables** screen, and **Select Predictand File**

Figure 9. Selecting the predictand file containing the observed precipitation data

Make sure to set the file filter to **All Files (*.*)** in order to make the **BelgradePrecOBS.txt** file visible

Select the **BOX_45_20E** folder to show the available predictor variables.

Figure 10. The selection of Predictor Variables

5.1 NCEP daily predictor variable codes and definitions

Code	Description	Units	Notes
dswr	Direct shortwave radiation	*	Derived from single cell
lftx	Surface lifted index	*	Temperature difference between an air parcel lifted adiabatically and the environment at a given height in the atmosphere
mslp	Mean sea level pressure	*	Derived from single cell
p_f	Geostrophic airflow velocity near the surface	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p_u	Zonal velocity component near the surface	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p_v	Meridional velocity component near the surface	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p_z	Vorticity near the surface	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p_th	Wind direction near the surface	° N	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p_zh	Divergence near the surface	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of mslp
p5_f	Geostrophic airflow velocity at 500 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p5_u	Zonal velocity component at 500 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p5_v	Meridional velocity component at 500 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p5_z	Vorticity at 500 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p5th	Wind direction at 500 hPa	° N	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p5zh	Divergence at 500 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 500 hPa levels
p8_f	Geostrophic airflow velocity at 850 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p8_u	Zonal velocity component at 850 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p8_v	Meridional velocity component at 850 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p8_z	Vorticity at 850 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p8th	Wind direction at 850 hPa	° N	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p8zh	Divergence at 850 hPa	*	Derived from a 3 x 3 array of 850 hPa levels
p500	500 hPa geopotential height	*	Derived from single cell
p850	850 hPa geopotential height	*	Derived from single cell
pottmp	Potential temperature	*	The temperature that an unsaturated air parcel would have if lowered (or raised) to a standard pressure
pr_wtr	Precipitable water	*	The depth of water in a column of the atmosphere, if all the water in that column were precipitated as rain
prec	Precipitation total	mm	Total liquid plus solid precipitation
r500	Relative humidity at 500 hPa height	*	Derived from single cell
r850	Relative humidity at 850 hPa height	*	Derived from single cell
rhum	Near surface relative humidity	*	Derived from single cell
shum	Near surface specific humidity	*	Derived from single cell
temp	Near surface air temperature	°C	Derived from single cell

* denotes a dimensionless Z-score with mean zero and standard deviation one

Visualize interactions between selected predictors (NCEP variables) and the predictand (in this case daily precipitation) using the Scatter Plot (Figure 11) or Correlation matrix (Figure 12):

Figure 11. Scatter plot

Figure 12. Correlation matrix

6. MODEL CALIBRATION

Figure 13. Model calibration

A file name needs to be defined for output (**Select Output PAR file**). This file will be the input for modeling in step

After setting up, the **Calibrate** button activates the calibration.

Calibration Results

File Help

Back Print Help

Predictand: BelgradePrecOBS.txt

Predictors:
ncep_p_zh.dat
ncep_pr_wtr.dat
ncep_prec.dat

Unconditional Statistics

Month	RSquared	SE	FRatio	Prop Correct
January	0.0854	0.4740	54.92	0.6520
February	0.0677	0.4785	38.87	0.6311
March	0.0875	0.4612	56.40	0.6621
April	0.1257	0.4622	81.82	0.6637
May	0.1410	0.4594	96.48	0.6548
June	0.1261	0.4628	82.11	0.6433
July	0.1309	0.4339	88.57	0.7018
August	0.1441	0.4153	99.02	0.7436
September	0.1599	0.4249	108.26	0.7316
October	0.1517	0.4233	105.12	0.7391
November	0.0829	0.4660	51.41	0.6602
December	0.0613	0.4816	38.38	0.6203
Mean	0.1137	0.4536	75.11	0.6753

Conditional Statistics

Month	RSquared	SE	FRatio
January	0.0402	0.4110	20.4257
February	0.0359	0.4230	12.1574
March	0.0604	0.4182	22.5285
April	0.0570	0.4259	12.0092
May	0.0917	0.4596	10.5076
June	0.0788	0.4922	19.0598
July	0.0965	0.5004	18.4192
August	0.0528	0.4712	10.6908
September	0.0732	0.4808	14.6878
October	0.0393	0.4632	12.4914
November	0.0348	0.4325	11.3434
December	0.0309	0.4455	11.8643
Mean	0.0576	0.4520	14.6821

Figure 14. Calibration results

7. WEATHER GENERATION (USING OBSERVED PREDICTORS)

Figure 15. Generating model output

The input file (**Select input file - BelgradeObs.par**) was generated in the previous step (6. **Model calibration**).

Select Output File defines the name for the modelled

8. STATISTICAL ANALYSES

Figure 16. Calculating statistics of the modelled output (BelgradeModel.out)

First the input file has to be selected under **Select Input File** (BelgradeModel.out that was calculated in [step 7.](#))

After setting the statistical test and selecting **Statistics**, the results will be written in the output file (**Select Output File, BelgradeModStat.txt**)

Statistics Selection

File Edit Help

Back Reset

Generic Tests

- Mean
- Maximum
- Minimum
- Sum
- Variance
- Median
- Count
- Extreme range
- Peaks over threshold
- Peaks below threshold
- Percentile
- Inter-quartile range
- Autocorrelation
- Skewness
- Maximum N-day total
- Minimum range

Conditional Tests

- Percentage wet
- Mean dry spell length
- Mean wet spell length
- Maximum dry spell length
- Maximum wet spell length
- SD dry spell length
- SD wet spell length
- Peaks over threshold
- POT as % of total
- Mean wet-day persistence
- Mean dry-day persistence
- Correlation for spell lengths
- Median wet spell length
- Median dry spell length

Delta Periods

Percentage Difference
 Absolute Difference

Base Start:
 Period A Start:
 Period B Start:
 Period C Start:

Base End:
 Period A End:
 Period B End:
 Period C End:

Figure 17. Up to 8 statistical tests can be selected

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR: BelgradeModel.OUT

Analysis Start Date: 01/01/1949
 Analysis End Date: 31/12/2017
 Ensemble Member(s): Ensemble Member(s): ALL

Month	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Dry-spell	Wet-spell	Max_dspel	Max_wspel
January	3.594	43.057	0.001	2.261	1.764	12.450	8.800
February	3.581	48.306	0.001	2.238	1.762	12.250	8.800
March	4.310	64.228	0.001	2.612	1.608	15.150	7.200
April	4.359	53.043	0.001	2.371	1.773	13.600	9.000
May	5.017	60.204	0.001	2.362	1.852	12.400	10.100
June	6.769	83.182	0.001	2.404	1.739	13.600	9.650
July	6.657	82.280	0.001	3.240	1.528	18.850	6.950
August	5.995	63.890	0.001	3.679	1.457	21.450	6.600
September	5.736	74.949	0.001	3.279	1.505	19.100	6.950
October	4.933	65.521	0.001	3.229	1.486	19.750	6.650
November	4.601	62.422	0.001	2.562	1.648	14.700	8.150
December	4.156	48.144	0.001	2.260	1.764	11.900	8.650
Winter	3.792	58.703	0.001	2.320	1.795	14.350	10.900
Spring	4.580	75.116	0.001	2.539	1.774	16.800	10.650
Summer	6.523	91.787	0.001	3.225	1.629	26.300	9.800
Autumn	5.048	89.196	0.001	3.158	1.566	22.750	8.550
Annual	4.887	101.525	0.001	2.826	1.707	27.800	12.200
Standard Deviations of Results							
January	0.171	10.971	0.000	0.062	0.052	1.830	1.600
February	0.125	13.138	0.000	0.095	0.059	2.211	2.182
March	0.161	21.359	0.000	0.075	0.028	3.336	1.288
April	0.211	13.649	0.000	0.087	0.051	2.557	1.265
May	0.168	10.678	0.000	0.065	0.039	1.744	1.609
June	0.320	16.832	0.000	0.085	0.044	2.010	1.797
July	0.365	17.177	0.000	0.089	0.043	3.336	1.023
August	0.292	17.073	0.001	0.121	0.044	3.369	1.281
September	0.316	19.268	0.000	0.098	0.045	3.161	1.203
October	0.272	24.976	0.000	0.121	0.032	2.861	0.910
November	0.219	16.632	0.000	0.090	0.045	2.027	1.062
December	0.190	10.543	0.000	0.066	0.031	1.411	1.398
Winter	0.090	11.950	0.000	0.054	0.029	1.459	1.446
Spring	0.089	15.124	0.000	0.043	0.026	2.804	1.236
Summer	0.220	17.724	0.000	0.082	0.028	5.207	1.661
Autumn	0.149	20.684	0.000	0.040	0.017	2.755	1.071
Annual	0.057	17.707	0.000	0.031	0.014	4.600	2.015

Figure 19. Results for statistics calculation for the modelled data

To calculate the statistics for observed values the **Observed** option has to be selected under **Data Source**.

The **BelgradePrecObs.txt** is selected for input and the statistics will be saved in the **BelgradeOBS_st.txt** file.

Figure 20. Settings for calculating statistics for observed data (note that the analysis start date is 1961)

Figure 21. Results of the Summary statistics for the Belgrad daily observed precipitation dataset

9. GRAPHING MODEL OUTPUT

Figure 22. Settings for comparing results from measured modelled data statistics

Figure 23. Line chart comparison of Mean observed and modelled precipitation

Figure 24. Comparison of observed data (BelgradeObs.txt) and the ensemble mean (based on d20 members) of SDSM model output(BelgradeModel.OUT) in Excel

Figure 25. Settings for **Frequency Analysis**

Scatter Plot

File Edit Help

Figure 26. Example quantile-quantile plot

Figure 27. Results of Frequency analysis - GEV and Gumbel

Figure 28. Settings for time series analysis

Figure 29. Annual precipitation totals 1948-2017. Note that SDSM can reconstruct downscaled information from the NCEP predictor variables for periods without meteorological observations (in this case for 1948-1960).

10. SCENARIO GENERATION (WITHOUT CLIMATE MODEL INPUT)

The screenshot shows the 'Scenario Generator' application window. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, Help), a breadcrumb navigation bar (Home, Quality Control, Transform Data, Screen Variables, Calibrate Model, Weather Generator), and a toolbar (Reset, Generate, Settings). The main settings area is divided into several sections:

- Select Input File:** A button labeled 'Select Input File' with the file path 'File: BelgradeModel.OUT' below it.
- File Start Date:** A text input field containing '01/01/1948'.
- Ensemble Size:** A text input field containing '1'.
- Select Output File:** A button labeled 'Save To File' with the file path 'File: ModelScenario.OUT' below it.
- Conditional Process?:** A checked checkbox with a text input field for 'Event Threshold' set to '0'. This section is highlighted with a red box.
- Treatments:**
 - Occurrence:** A checked checkbox. 'Frequency change:' is set to '0 %'. Radio buttons for 'Stochastic' (selected) and 'Forced' are present. 'Preserve Total?' is unchecked.
 - Mean:** A checked checkbox. Radio buttons for 'Factor' (selected, set to '20 %') and 'Addition' (set to '0') are present. This section is highlighted with a red box.
 - Variance:** An unchecked checkbox. 'Factor:' is set to '0 %'.
 - Trend:** An unchecked checkbox. Radio buttons for 'Linear' (set to '0 /year'), 'Exponential' (set to '1'), and 'Logistic' (set to '1') are present.

Figure 30. Scenario generator settings

11. APPENDIX 1 – RESOLVING ISSUES WITH RUNNING THE SOFTWARE

1. When running the software, the following error may appear

Figure 31. Error message after running the software

Solution:

Find the folder where SDSM is installed (Usually C:/Program files/SDSM

Find the **sdsms60.exe** file and rename it to **sdsms.exe**

2. The Settings can not be saved and the following error message appears:

Figure 32. Error after saving the Settings

Possible solution:

Make sure that the operating system setting for decimal separator is point and comma for digit grouping symbol.

Settings for Windows 10

The screenshot shows the Windows Settings application. At the top, a search bar contains 'region settings'. Below the search bar, a list of results is shown, with 'Region settings' (System settings) highlighted. To the right, the 'Region' settings page is open. It shows 'Country or region' set to 'United Kingdom', 'Regional format' set to 'English (United Kingdom)', and 'Regional format data' for the Gregorian Calendar. A red box highlights the 'Related settings' link at the bottom right of the page.

Clock and Region

The screenshot shows the Windows Control Panel window for 'Clock and Region'. The breadcrumb path is 'Control Panel > Clock and Region'. On the left, a list of control panel categories is shown, with 'Clock and Region' selected. On the right, there are two main links: 'Date and Time' (Set the time and date | Change the time zone | Add clocks for different time zones) and 'Region' (Change date, time, or number formats). The 'Region' link is highlighted with a red box.

Region ✕

Formats **Administrative**

Format:
English (United Kingdom) ▾

[Language preferences](#)

Date and time formats

Short date:	dd/MM/yyyy ▾
Long date:	dd MMMM yyyy ▾
Short time:	HH:mm ▾
Long time:	HH:mm:ss ▾
First day of week:	Monday ▾

Examples

Short date:	23/04/2022
Long date:	23 April 2022
Short time:	13:38
Long time:	13:38:18

Additional settings...

OK Cancel Apply

Figure 33. Region Settings in Windows 10

3. When working on dual display systems with two monitors or a monitor / projector system, **SDSM opens new windows only on the Default Display (Display 1)**. This issue can interfere during presentations through a projector or online applications such as Zoom, MS Teams, Discord, etc.

Solution: Chose a display (e.g. Projector or the shared screen for the application) for working with SDSM and make it the **Default Display (Display 1)**.

LEGAL NOTICE Neither the Research Executive Agency/European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Research Executive Agency/Commission is responsible for the use, which might be made, of the following information.

The views expressed in this report are those of the authors and the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

© EXtremeClimTwin Consortium, 2020

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged